

Inherited structural plays and their reactivation within the recent stress field as a means to predict blind geothermal systems in orogenic belts

Timothy C. Schmid¹, Marco Herwegh¹, Alfons Berger¹, Herfried Madritsch², Tobias Diehl³, Daniela B. van den Heuvel¹, Christoph Wanner¹, Larryn W. Diamond¹,

¹ Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Baltzerstrasse 1 + 3, CH-3012 Bern

² Federal Office of Topography swisstopo, Seftigenstrasse 264, CH-3084 Wabern

³ Swiss Seismological Service (SED), ETH Zürich, Sonneggstrasse 5, CH-8092 Zürich

timothy.schmid@unibe.ch

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ABSTRACT

Fault-bound hydrothermal systems are a major exploration target in Switzerland to extract hot water for electricity and space heating. The Rhône Valley in the SW Swiss Alps is a promising area for geothermal energy given its numerous known hot springs, several of which are commercially exploited. Further unknown geothermal systems are likely to exist along regional-scale faults in the Rhône Valley, at sites where the interconnectivity of certain fault structures creates fluid pathways. Finding these favourable settings along the valley floor, where demand for geothermal heat and electricity would be greatest, and understanding their fluid flow geometries is hindered by the often thick cover of unconsolidated, Quaternary deposits. We present a regional-scale kinematic model that explains the occurrences of known hot springs and that predicts favourable locations for blind hydrothermal systems. The model thus serves as a guide for future geothermal exploration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Zones of brittle deformation often provide flow paths for hydrothermal fluids due to their high permeability. This is particularly true for active fault zones, where reoccurring slip and refracturing counteract clogging caused by mineral precipitation. The Rhône Valley in the Canton of Valais, SW Swiss Alps, hosts numerous geothermal springs that are commercially exploited. The springs discharge meteoric water that originally infiltrated at high altitudes on the surrounding mountains and circulated deeply through the hot, fractured crystalline basement before rising to low points in the topography (e.g., Diamond et al., 2018; Sonney and Vuataz, 2009; Wanner et al., 2019). Understanding the fault systems and associated brittle structures that control the ascent of these thermal waters is a key to exploring for geothermal energy in

this region. Such understanding can also inspire exploration in comparable orogenic settings elsewhere.

The evident control that regional-scale faults in the Rhône Valley exert on geothermal systems arises from the faults having certain favourable orientations for dilatant behaviour within the region's recent stress field. They thus tend to generate new pore space in their damage zones as they slip. If the pores in such zones are hydraulically connected, then permeability for circulating water is also likely to be enhanced. Hence, fluid flow becomes feasible through country rocks that are otherwise impermeable. Such permeable zones favourable for geothermal activity may occur along individual faults or at fault intersections.

Favourable fault systems occur within the Rhône Valley floor, where demand for heat and electricity is greatest, but they mostly remain hidden under hundreds of metres of unconsolidated sediments, hindering the direct study of their geometry and interconnectivity. To understand the interplay between deep-fluid flow and permeable fault systems, it is therefore necessary to draw on indirect observations that provide insights into regional-scale tectonic features.

Our ongoing GeoTex research project aims to assess the geothermal potential of the Rhône Valley by combining field-based structural observations with seismological and remote sensing data to characterize fault geometries, fault kinematics and fault rocks in the vicinity of known thermal springs. We also integrate into our analysis exposures of paleo-fluid pathways along major Alpine structures marked by veins and rock alteration. Analysis of this diverse data allows evaluation of the role of fault systems as fluid pathways within the recent regional stress and hydraulic fields. Given the history of strong vertical exhumation (Schlatter, 2014) and the apparent constancy of the stress field in the Valais region over the last millions of years (e.g., Truttmann, 2024), the studied fault zones are interpreted to have formed in a neotectonic regime that is very similar to the present-day active tectonic

setting. Within this context, we propose a regional-scale kinematic model that, to a first order, explains the presence and location of known hot springs in response to the regional-scale active tectonics.

2. TECTONIC SETTING AND HOT SPRINGS

The Rhône Valley in the SW Swiss Alps approximately marks the boundary between the Helvetic tectonic units in the north and the Penninic units in the south (Fig. 1). Their architecture results from the Mesozoic paleogeography of the former European passive continental margin, with the Helvetic and Penninic units reflecting the proximal and distal sedimentary

deposits, respectively (e.g., Pfiffner, 2014; Cardello and Mancktelow, 2014). In addition, the Penninics in this region also contain blocks of the former Briançonnais basement swell. During Late Eocene to Early Miocene Alpine continental collision, the Penninic units became stacked on top of the Helvetics along the Pennine Basal Thrust (Cardello et al., 2019). Following uplift and erosion, the geographic regions now exposing the Helvetics and Penninics roughly coincide with the two geodynamically distinct domains that we have identified. The lowermost Helvetic units are attached to the crystalline basement that is exposed as the Aar/Gastern massif in the NE and the Aiguilles Rouges/Mont Blanc massifs in the SW (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Main tectonic units and known geothermal springs in the Rhône Valley. Based on our analysis, we distinguish two geodynamically distinct, northern and southern domains (see Chapter 3). Top left inset shows the region of interest (ROI; Rhône Valley) in Switzerland.

Due to the SW and NE plunges of their respective axes, the Aar/Gastern and Aiguilles Rouges massifs form a saddle-like structure north of the Rhône Valley floor, where Helvetic units are exposed in the so-called Rawil Depression.

Most of the southern domain is underlain by a low-angle normal fault plane, over which the exposed hanging-wall block is undergoing SW-directed orogenic extension. The traces of this plane to the north in the valley floor are manifested by the steeply-dipping dextral strike-slip Rhône Fault, whereas in the east the trace displays dip-slip character and is known as the

Simplon Fault. The entire trace is collectively termed the Rhône-Simplon Fault System (RSF; Fig. 1). However, the Rhône fault trace lies hidden under a package of unconsolidated (glaciofluvial and fluvial) sediments that are up to 800 m thick (e.g., Pfiffner, 2014) making it difficult to establish its exact geometry. The RSF initiated around 19-18 Ma (Campani et al., 2010; Egli et al., 2017; Mancktelow, 1985). Recent earthquakes suggest that this kinematic framework is still active today with a transition from ductile to brittle deformation in the upper 10 kilometres (e.g., Lee et al., 2023) and is undergoing comparatively rapid exhumation (Schlatter, 2014).

Numerous commercially exploited thermal springs occur within the Rhône Valley. All of these discharge meteoric water that infiltrated at high altitudes on the surrounding mountains and circulated deeply through the fractured crystalline basement. Given a geothermal gradient in the area of about 28 °C/km, meteoric waters must have reached considerable depths. For the geothermal springs at Grimsel pass (Fig. 1) Diamond et al. (2018) suggested circulation depths down to 10 km based on hydrogeochemical data and modelling; e.g., roughly down to the earlier mentioned brittle-ductile transition. This suggests that regional-scale fault zones have acted as fluid pathways. In the Rhône Valley, the proximity of the RSF to some of the hot springs (from SW to NE: Saxon, Saillon, Brigerbad) make it a viable candidate for providing such pathways. However, most of the known hot springs are situated further away from the RSF either to the north (from SW to NE: Val d'Illicz, Lavey-ley-Bains, Leukerbad, Grimsel pass) or within the Penninic units (Combioula, Evolène), suggesting that additional structures must control fluid flow in those hydrothermal systems, or at least steer their outflow.

3. DATA SET

Our data sets comprise remote-sensed lineaments, field data from structural observations such as fault kinematics and fault geometries, as well as satellite-derived crustal motions, a set of relocated hypocentres and, earthquake focal mechanisms. This allows us to develop a regional-scale kinematic model to assess the role of individual fault systems as fluid pathways and, eventually, to detect active blind geothermal systems within the Rhône Valley.

3.1 Remote-sensed lineament maps

Faults were mapped on a 1:10 000 scale using the swissALTI3D hill shade model (swisstopo) to detect lineaments based on morphological expressions. Additional field observations as well as data from the Swiss Geological Atlas (swisstopo) were integrated in this mapping. For the valley floor, where structures remain hidden below several hundred meters of unconsolidated rocks, we used gravimetric data (Gravimetric Atlas 100, swisstopo) and bedrock data to further constrain individual segments of the RSF.

3.2 Structural field data

Structural observations (i.e., characterization of fault system orientations, kinematics, fault intersections) as well as mineralogical evidence of paleo-hydrothermal fluid flow were collected during short field campaigns in the vicinity of known hot springs. Evidence of paleo-hydrothermal fluid flow near known hot springs was found where two or more fault systems with different orientations intersect. These faults have predominantly steep (vertical to subvertical) dips with NW-SE and NE-SW to E-W strikes (Fig. 2a). NE-SW striking faults are up to several kilometres in length and occasionally are initiated along shear zones indicating ductile precursors within the Aar/Gastern and Aiguilles Rouges Massifs (e.g., Truttmann, 2024).

Figure 2: Field observations of hydrothermal paleo-fluid flow. a) Stereo net indicating the two regional main fault trends. b) Calcite fibres indicating dextral oblique-slip along a NE-SW trending fault plane. c) Damage zones with pyrite alteration (now rusted by surficial weathering) along fault intersection (i.e., intersection of visible faults with the image plane), with fractured but hydrothermally unaltered rocks in-between. d) Chalcidony precipitation along fault intersection indicates past hydrothermal fluid flow.

At the Rhône Valley floor, NE-SW striking faults were only found in the Area of Sion, where hills of Penninic bedrocks emerge from the surrounding by fluvio-glacial deposits. There, kinematic indicators clearly indicate transpressive dextral shear along brittle structures (Fig. 2b) that coincide with the steeply oriented foliation of folded Flysch units. Near locations of known hot springs within the valley floor, however, direct evidence of this strike-slip kinematics is scarce, as the bedrock is covered by fluvio-glacial sediments. NW-SE striking faults are nearly vertical in the basement units of the Aar/Gastern and Aiguilles Rouges Massifs but dip at moderate angles towards SW within the Rawil depression (Truttmann, 2024). It is possible that this fault set is the expression of orogen-parallel extension that became reactivated in the recent stress field as antithetic strike-slip faults with a sinistral shear sense. NW-SE striking faults are often characterized by haloes of hydrothermal alteration (rusted pyrite) along more intensely fractured zones surrounded by unaltered host rock (Fig. 2c) and by quartz and chalcidony precipitates along fault planes (Fig. 2d), attesting to passage of hot fluids long before exhumation of the outcrops.

The occurrence of enhanced porosity and hydrothermal mineral precipitation along fault intersections suggests that thermal waters flow vertically along 1D pipe-like channels within fault intersections (Micklethwaite and

Cox, 2004; Belgrano et al., 2016). Whereas the documented channels (now partly clogged with hydrothermal minerals) represent paleo-fluid flow pathways, they serve as analogues for upflow zones that are active today at depth. Besides the role of fault intersections and local fault dilatancy planes (Egli et al., 2018), hydrothermal fluid discharge at the Grimsel pass is related to a large-scale, initially ductile (i.e., shear zone), fault system, in which branches and fault linkages underwent brittle reactivation. The resulting steep breccias and damage zones with open pores have acted as major upflow zones for thermal fluids (Belgrano et al., 2016; Egli et al., 2018).

3.3 GNSS-derived crustal movements

Satellite-based geodesy (GNSS surface velocities) show that horizontal velocity components undergo a prominent change in direction across the Rhône valley floor. Velocities in the NW show a general movement towards N/NW while velocities in the S/SE indicate a general horizontal movement that is directed to the SW (Fig. 3). Associated horizontal crustal velocities range between 0.14 to 0.8 mm/a in the northern and 0.18 to 0.6 mm/a in the southern domain.

The valley floor depicts the boundary between these two distinct domains (i.e., north domain, south domain) but it remains unclear whether the valley floor itself is part of one of the two domains or whether it represents a rather gradual transition zone. However, kinematics characteristically attributed to the north domain were found on either side at the flanks in vicinity of the valley floor suggesting that the valley floor itself is the marginal part of the northern domain. Either way, considering the surface velocities, the valley floor comprising the Rhône fault system, would represent a transtensional boundary between the two domains and is therefore an excellent candidate for geothermal exploration.

Figure 3: Horizontal GNSS surface velocities for the Rhône Valley with reference to stable Europe. Azimuth refers to the direction of motion. Arrow size is according to reference vector in the legend.

3.4 Relocated hypocentres

Relocated hypocentres (Diehl et al., 2024) cover all seismic events over the past 40 years, with a maximum magnitude of 4.1. In the Rhône Valley, the majority of the hypocentres lie within the upper 12 km of the crust (Fig. 4). Two prominent clusters are visible in the north domain striking parallel to the fold axes of the NE-SW trending Aar and Aiguilles Rouges massifs and, in the south domain, as a curved shape parallel to the Penninic basal thrust (see Fig. 1). Fewer events plot in the eastern part of the northern domain and a denser cluster occurs near Val d'Illiez, striking parallel to the NNW-SSE branch of the Rhône Valley floor.

Figure 4: Hypocentre distribution (Diehl et al., 2024) within the Rhône Valley for depths ≤ 12 km. Colours refer to the depth. Black dashed line marks the domain boundary.

3.5 Focal mechanisms and regional stress field

Earthquake focal mechanisms derived from first-motion polarities of P-waves (Fig. 4; Diehl et al., 2024) support the discrimination of two separate domains as the regional stress fields show two domains of distinct principal stress orientation (Fig. 5), first described by Maurer et al. (1997) and later by Kastrup et al. (2004), as follows.

The northern domain is transtensional with a dominant NW-SE maximum principal stress orientation and a minimum principal stress component striking NE-SW. With both components subhorizontal, the northern domain stress regime yields dominant strike-slip faulting and surface displacements towards the NW (Figs. 3 and 5). In contrast, the southern domain exhibits a near-vertical maximum principal stress orientation that yields normal faults striking ENE-WSW to E-W and with current surface motion towards the SW (Figs. 3 and 5). In both domains, strike-slip to oblique-slip faulting is present.

Figure 5: Subset of focal mechanisms of Diehl et al. (2024). Large black and white arrows depict the regional stress field (Kastrup et al., 2004). Black dashed line marks the domain boundary.

4. REGIONAL-SCALE KINEMATIC MODEL

Using additional lineament data sets from literature (Bistacchi and Massironi, 2000; Champagnac et al., 2003), as well as the aforementioned data (i.e., field data, hypocentres and focal mechanisms) we established a synoptic regional-scale fault system map for the northern and southern flanks of the Rhône Valley as well as in the valley floor itself. Where supported by data, we also attribute distinct kinematics to the displayed faults (Fig. 6).

The domain in the northern valley flank consists of NE-SW trending dextral strike-slip faults. It is noteworthy that in the western part, where seismic activity is high (i.e., between Lavey-les-Bains and Leukerbad) these NE-SW faults are partially connected via dextral E-W trending faults (Figs. 4 and 6). In the eastern part, however, E-W trending fault segments are absent with the NE-SW faults delineating a seemingly continuous dextral strike-slip zone between Grimselpass and Leukerbad (Fig. 6), that is traceable due to its morphological expression (Musso Piantelli, 2023). Additionally, sinistral NNW-SSE trending strike-slip segments are located near Val d’Illiez and possibly

within the NNW-SSE striking branch of the Rhône Valley (i.e., near Lavey-ley-Bains) and Leukerbad (Fig. 6). In the context of the regional stress field, these steeply-dipping segments exhibit a favourable orientation for NE-SW extension along oblique-slip faults with sinistral shear.

The Rhône Valley floor comprises the Rhône Fault, which defines the boundary between the northern and southern domains. Its dextral strike-slip characteristics evident in field observations show that this part of the RSF is under the influence of the recent regional stress field of the north domain. Furthermore, gravimetry data (swisstopo) suggests that the Rhône Fault consists of several segments rather than one continuous fault. Their arrangement leads to several zones where these segments overlap. Owing to the transtensional crustal movements in the valley floor (as derived from GNSS data) and to the dextral character of the fault segments, their overlaps generate either zones of compression (i.e., if left-stepping; e.g., Truttmann et al., 2023) or dilation (i.e., if right-stepping). Only the latter are considered “favourable” as linkage of such segments may create steeply-dipping, dilatant and hence permeable channels. These facilitate relatively fast upflow of geothermal waters to the surface or to the contact with the overlying unconsolidated sediments. Notably the suspected blind geothermal systems in the Rhône Valley are expected to be strongly influenced by near conditions hydrogeological settings. It is expected that geothermal waters rising from the bedrock will rapidly mix with cold groundwaters in the unconsolidated Quaternary sediments.

The southern domain is underlain at depth by the low-angle Simplon normal fault, the trace of which trends NW-SE. Several valleys in this area show orientations that are compatible with presumed Simplon Fault parallel structures, expected to dip towards the SW. Such faults within the hanging-wall block of the Simplon low-angle normal fault would have a high dilation tendency due to their normal fault kinematics providing excellent pathways for geothermal waters. The southern domain further includes steeply-dipping E-W to NE-SW trending oblique-slip faults. Within the recent regional stress field such orientations are prone to normal faulting and hence, provide further fracture-related permeability for rapid upflow of geothermal waters.

Figure 6: Schematic interpretation map of the large-scale kinematic fault systems for the Rhône Valley. Orange shades refer to the large-scale fault systems of the north domain. Green lineaments depict segments of the Rhône fault system and blueish shades refer to the south domain. Black dashed line marks the domain boundary.

3. CONCLUSIONS

We have established a regional-scale kinematic model for the Rhône Valley based on structural field observations, remote-sensed lineament mapping as well as geodetic surface velocities and relocated earthquake hypocentre data. Calibrated with the location of known hot springs, this regional-scale model enables the identification of promising zones for blind geothermal systems, offering a valuable tool for future geothermal exploration in orogenic settings. The model describes two distinct geodynamic domains in the northern and southern flanks of the Rhône valley floor, each characterized by fault systems of differing kinematics. The buried valley floor, which lies near the boundary of the two domains, is assigned to the northern domain.

The northern domain is characterised by a regional stress field that promotes strike-slip faulting where dilatant structures strike NNW-SSE (i.e., WSW-ESE directed extension) to NW-SE (i.e., NE-SW directed extension). Within the valley floor, segments of the Rhône Fault dominantly strike NE-SW with a dextral sense of shear. Their orientation within the regional stress field prevents dilation but the overlaps between its various fault segments promotes local linkage

geometries where steep, dilatant channels may permit ascent of geothermal waters. The southern domain is subject to recent NNE-SSW extension which is expressed by dominantly normal to transtensional faulting focal mechanisms (e.g., Maurer et al., 1997; Lee et al., 2023) considered to be favourable for upflow of geothermal waters.

Most of the known hot springs lie within the vicinity of one of the above-mentioned dilatant structures in our kinematic model, suggesting that the hot spring locations are controlled by the regional scale fault systems of the Valais. Where this does not appear to be the case, complexities at local scale may explain the surficial outflow of hot springs. For example, the Grimsel pass hot spring occurs along a dextral NE-SW trending fault segment that is unfavourably oriented for dilatancy in the context of the recent stress field. However, at smaller scales the apparently straight fault strands reveal local, highly dilatant geometries: branches and fault intersections (Egli et al., 2018), linkage zones of fault segments, and bends along precursor ductile shear zones that underwent brittle reactivation (Belgrano et al., 2016). Such local fragmentations have also been documented by earthquake sequences near the valley floor (e.g.,

Truttmann et al., 2023) and likely can be expected elsewhere in the Rhône Valley.

Implications from these observations are twofold. First, local details in fault geometry must be taken into account as they play an important role in enabling upflow and may create dilatational structures at unexpected locations (see also Herwegh et al., this volume). Second, reactivation of inherited, formerly ductile structures may also generate dilatational structures (e.g., fault bends due to anastomosing shear zones) at unforeseen sites. Hence, once potentially dilatant structures are located, closer investigation of their second-order features at smaller scales (such as sealing sedimentary units or local structural irregularities and reactivation features) is crucial in order to detect blind geothermal systems.

In the forthcoming steps of the GeoTex project we will combine the findings of the structural analysis with the outcomes of hydrochemical analyses of geothermal waters from known hot springs and from subthermal groundwaters throughout the valley floor. These will permit development of maps that reveal favourable zones to explore for blind geothermal systems.

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